

COMPETITION BETWEEN ENGLAND AND RUSSIA IN CENTRAL ASIAN KHANATES.

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Annotation: *In this article, the Anglo-Russian rivalry in Central Asia in the 19th century, the diplomatic relations sent by Russia, the diplomatic relations sent by England, their efforts to establish their rule in the Central Asian khanates, and the cunning policy of Nicholas I.*

Key Word: *Bukhara, Khiva, Kokan, England, Russia, A. Burns, Ch. Stoddart.*

Annotatsiya: *Bu maqolada XIX asrda O`rta Osiyoda ingliz-rus raqobatchiligi, Rossiya tomonidan yuborilgan elchilik munosabatlari, Angliya tomonidan yuborilgan elchilik munosabatlari, Ularning O`rta Osiyo xonliklarida o`z hukmronligini o`rnatishi uchun olib borgan ishlari va Nikolay I tomonidan olib borilgan ayyorona siyosat.*

**Kalit so`zlar:** *Buxoro, Xiva, Qo`qon, Angliya, Rossiya, A.Byorns, Ch. Stoddart.*

At the beginning of the second half of the 19th century, Russia's policy of subjugating the Central Asian khanates posed a serious threat to the far-sighted plans of Great Britain in this regard. In various ways, England is trying to mobilize the countries of Central Asia against Russia. In 1831-1833, the lieutenant of the East India Company, Alexander Burns, came from India to Afghanistan, and from there to Bukhara as a tourist. The evidence and personal observations collected as a result of this "trip" led to the creation of a three-volume book called "Trip to Bukhara". A. Burns' comments about the Uzbek people are noteworthy: "Uzbeks are humble and

sincere in their dealings. Since they did not know who I was, they did not hesitate to talk about everything, from their rulers and politics to the state of the market. By means of its diplomats, tourists and spies, England tried to organize the khanates of Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand into an alliance against Russia. For this purpose, they sent officers such as Connolly, Burns, Archie Todd, J. Abbot and Shakespeare, who knew Persian and Turkish languages well, to the Uzbek khanates. According to some sources, A. Connolly met Khiva Khan and told him, "There is only one way to save Uzbek states from being invaded by foreign countries. If there is one, it means to have a good relationship with each other and help each other." Khan of Khiva Olloquli Khan, when he heard that the Russians were planning to attack again in the spring, sent his ambassadors to Istanbul and to the British and asked for help. English officers J. Abbott and Shakespeare arrived at the Khan of Khiva, who had not received any news from the Turkish state. They told Khan of Khiva that he should free the Russian prisoners in the capital and not leave an excuse for the upcoming conflict. In fact, with the release of the captives, there were no more excuses to start a new war, and Perovsky was forced to postpone the campaign. Seeing that the danger has been eliminated, Olloqulikhan sent an ambassador named Qutbiddinkhoja to Istanbul and warned the Turks about the situation. Olloqulikhan also sent ambassadors to the British government for their help in ensuring peace.

The British government at this time Colonel Ch. Stoddart was sent to Bukhara. When Nasrullah Khan heard that Stoddart was coming to Bukhara, he ordered him to dismount and walk at a leisurely pace before entering the city and hand over his weapons. But Stoddart forgets the rules of Asian order and ignores the orders of the ruler of Bukhara. Nasrullah Khan was forced to accept Stoddart after swallowing his pain. Amir does not believe that his real goal is to establish a friendly relationship, not espionage, and asks him for a relevant document. Since Colonel Stoddart does not have such a document, the amir arrests him. The detention of the ambassadors in Bukhara forces the British government to try to free them. The British government tried to influence the emir of Bukhara first through the Khan of

Khiva, and then through the Turkish government. But when the document requested by the emir of Bukhara did not arrive, Stoddart was thrown into prison. Captain Connolly, who heard this news, leaves for Bukhara. Amir also arrests him because he does not have the necessary documents. Two British officers meet in Bukhara prison. In 1842, they were executed as spies.

In the second half of the 19th century, when it comes to the reasons for the relatively easy occupation of Turkestan land by Russia, in many cases, it is said that the rulings and decrees of the Kokan, Khiva khanates and the Bukhara Emirate in the country were not compatible with each other. This opinion is correct to a certain extent. After all, even before the Russian invasion, there were various disputes between these three khanates, they attacked each other's lands and robbed the inhabitants. However, after the Russian emperors decided to conquer Central Asia, they constantly tried to create an impenetrable chasm between the khanates. When the ruling circles of Russia sent spies in the guise of merchants and tourists and became thoroughly aware of the real situation in the khanates, "diplomacy" began to take more and more place in the invasion plans of the Ulam. In particular, on the one hand, they hid their evil goals from the ambassadors of Kokand, Bukhara and Khiva sent to Russia, pretending that their work, such as building military fortifications in areas close to the Khanate, coordinating river ports for future attacks, was being done in the interests of the Khanate. they want to do it. On the other hand, as the time of the invasion of Turonzamin approached, they managed to implement diplomacy aimed at deliberately intensifying the conflict between the three khans with the participation of the emperor and his closest followers.

One of these political tricks was in the spring of 1842 when the Khanate of Kokand was invaded by Emir Nasrullah, plundered and mass executions were carried out, and as if that was not enough, the entire territory of the Khanate was officially declared a part of the Emirate of Bukhara by Emperor Nicholas of Russia. In the letter sent by I to the emir: The emperor, knowing full well that emir Nasrullah was the main cause of this unjust war between the two khanates, expressed his

satisfaction with the emir's victory in Kokan and wrote to him as if showing a compliment: It is necessary to eliminate the struggle for the throne in blood. After that, the lands from Turkestan and Tashkent to the banks of the Syrdarya, from Jizzakh to the borders of Oratepa, Khojand, Kokan, Margilan and Kashgar will be in the hands of your majesty and we want you to rule. ". Only three months before this letter, on February 25, 1842, in a letter sent to Muhammad Alikhan through the ambassador of the Khanate, Muhammad Khalil Sahibzada, the same Nicholas I himself said: "Your desire to have regular friendly relations with the mighty Russian state it was very nice for us to know. We accept your good intentions with full respect. We believe that your sincere concern to establish friendly neighborly relations will lead to successful results in the future. We wish you all the best." Nicholas I, the emperor of a world-famous and powerful country like Russia, who only three months ago wished all the good things of the world to the Kokan Khanate, now sees no injustice and injustice. saying, giving him the impression of a great compliment. But after some time, the same territories were trampled under the feet of Russian soldiers: in addition to turning the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate into vassals of the empire, the name of the Kokand Khanate was completely erased from the world map.

It is known from historical sources that in order to justify his invasion campaign, Emir Nasrullah came out with a claim that Muhammad Ali Khan committed an act contrary to Sharia by marrying a concubine whom his father wanted to marry. The intelligent historian of that time, Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat, writes in his book "History of Ferghana" about what actually caused this work of Amir Nasrullah: "Umar Khan was fascinated by the praise of Posh Shah Khan who said, ``I will take it," Amir Nasrullah actually caused this and came to see Muhammad Ali Khan as a rebel and a sinner in the eyes of the people, violated the Sharia, and needed to be reprimanded. He finally achieved his goal and took that concubine to Bukhara. In Mirza Alim Mushrif's work "Ansab us-salatin wa tawarikh ul-khawaqin", "another reason for Amir Nasrullah's invasion is emphasized: there was a negotiation

between Ferghana Khan Muhammad Ali Khan and Amir Nasrullah regarding the ownership of the fortress named Bashoghir has passed. After not giving the fortress to the emir Nasrullah, the emir easily captured the fortress with his army, then marched to the cities of Oratepa and Khojand, captured Ferghana and executed the khan and his relatives. All the historians of that time stated that the reason for the invasion of Kokan by Emir Nasrullo was, first of all, when Muhammad Ali Khan strengthened the Bashoghir fortress bordering the emirate for the inviolability of the borders of the Kokan Khanate, and also, the beauty of Posh Shah Khan's concubine whom Muhammad Ali Khan married. They see when the emir, who heard her riff, falls in love with her in absentia. When it comes to this barbarity of Amir Nasrullah and many other deeds, the historians of that time noted that the people were very dissatisfied with him and began to call the amir not by his name, but by the nickname "Batir the Butcher". .

By means of its diplomats, tourists and spies, England tried to organize the khanates of Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand into an alliance against Russia. In order to prevent this union from appearing, the Russian emperors threatened by sending their ambassadors and ordered to limit any communication with the British. In addition, the Russian tsars tried very hard to bring the relationship between the 3 khanates here to a very bad level. This led to the transformation of Central Asian khanates into colonies of the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century.

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